

Betel nut derivatives binding on DNA: A computational study

Manickam Akila ¹, Beutline Malgija M², Mohanmaran Soumya Rachael¹, Freddy AJ*

¹*Department of Zoology, Madras Christian College, Chennai 600059.*

²*Computational Science Laboratory, MCC-MRF Innovation Park, Madras Christian College,
Chennai 600059*

**Corresponding Author, Department of Zoology, Madras Christian College, Chennai 600059.*

ABSTRACT

Betel nut (BN) chewing is a tradition which dates back thousands of years. The bitter poultice is an acquired taste and although it is not clear why the people of the Pacific originally began to chew betel nut, the habit has been passed down through the generations and now provides a cultural link to their past. Carcinogens in BN can induce DNA damage which is an extremely common event in a cell's lifetime. Chemically induced damages generate harmful by-products, leading to alterations in the genetic makeup ultimately causing cancerous lesions.

Objective:

Identification of DNA adduct formation of BN derivatives, Arecoline, Homo arecoline and Nicotine on DNA emphasizing their potential genotoxic effects.

Method

Molecular docking and Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulations of Arecoline, Homo arecoline and Nicotinic acid were done using the desmond module (academic version) of Schrodinger software suite.

Results

All three molecules examined have shown potential for covalent interaction with DNA, particularly within the minor groove, as indicated by the presence of N+H interactions. To further substantiate these observations, molecular dynamics simulations of DNA-Arecoline, DNA-Homo Arecoline, and DNA-Nicotinic acid complexes were conducted, revealing stability across the 50 ns simulation period.

Conclusion

Methoxycarbonyl group of the ligands play crucial role in forming hydrogen bonds with the DNA molecule by acting as electron acceptors and are capable of forming DNA adducts,

suggesting possible DNA damage and associated toxicological effects. the bioactivity of these compounds, including their roles as ion channel modulators and GPCR ligands, alongside observed neurotoxicity, respiratory toxicity, and potential blood-brain barrier toxicity, emphasizes the need for further investigation.

Keywords: Betel nut, Arecoline, Molecular Dynamics, DNA adduct, Docking

INTRODUCTION

Environment encompasses genetic and non-genetic factors such as diet, lifestyle and infectious agents, in this broad sense, the environment is implicated in the causation of the majority of diseases including human cancers, as has been demonstrated since the 1960s(1) . In the past decade with an increase in globalization and industrialization there is an overwhelming increase of lifestyle associated diseases like cancer, diabetes and other metabolic disorders (2). Oral cancer was described in the Sushruta Samhita, a treatise on Indian surgery written in Sanskrit around 600 B.C., and literary references cite the habit of chewing betel quid (betel leaf, areca nut and lime) in India to be at least 2,000 years. It is estimated that at least 600 million individuals consume areca nuts in one form or another worldwide (3–5). The major areca nut alkaloids are arecoline, arecaidine, arecolidine, guvacoline and guvacine. Arecoline (1,2,4,5,-tetrahydro-1-methyl-pyridine- carboxylic acid; molecular weight 155.19) is the most abundant alkaloid of areca (6) . There are strong indications to the association of betel quid chewing with cancers of the mouth, oropharyngeal cavity, and upper parts of the digestive tract (IARC, 2004, 2022), moreover, chewing and smoking habits interact synergistically for these cancers (8,9). Although some pathological (10), epidemiological (11) and genetic studies on oral cancer and precancer have been previously reported, the incidence of oral cancer is still very high in these countries and only a few efforts have been carried out for its prevention (12,13). In the past 3 years out of 156,000 reported cancer cases, 21000 cases were related to oral cavity which approximately accounted for 13% of cases with tongue being the most common site (44.22%), buccal mucosa (14.69%), followed by lip 3.49% (14). In many countries the mortality rate is increasing among younger men associated both smoking and chewing, separately and in conjunction with betel quid chewing with other factors such as poor oral hygiene, nutritional factors and certain occupational exposures (15). With the impact of xenobiotic compounds predisposing a cell to genomic instability, a tendency to acquire mutations, rearrangements, adduct formations, sister chromatid exchanges, chromosomal deletions or gains could drive the cell to carcinogenesis (16). Nuclear content – DNA being the predominant molecular target for all or several interactions there is lacuna in understanding ligand or a chemical compound binding to the DNA. Understanding the interaction compounds to DNA with Autodoc could reveal binding sites on the DNA and develop prediction models. We propose that this model could be used for other targets to get

valuable results and could possibly become a standard protocol to make personalized therapy possible (17–19).

MATERIALS & METHODS

Retrieval of Structures

The structures of the selected molecules Arecoline, Homo Arecoline and Nicotinic acid were retrieved from PubChem(20).

Physico-chemical Properties and Toxicity Prediction

The physico-chemical properties of the given compounds were determined using QikProp and SwissADME. The toxicity of the molecules was predicted using ProTox-II(21). Qikprop predicts around 30 descriptions and the important parameters like molecular weight, logP, donor HB (hydrogen bond), and acceptor HB analyses Lipinski's Rule of Five²² molecular volume, polar surface area (PSA) and Jorgensen's Rule of Three were considered. ProTox-II predicts toxicities of small molecules based on their similarity with already known toxic compounds.

DNA and ligand Preparation

Short strands of DNA molecules of the target gene CDK4 was drawn using Maestro. The ligand molecules Arecoline, Homo Arecoline and Nicotinic acid were retrieved from PubChem (Fig_1).

Figure_1: 2D structures of the chosen ligands A) Nicotinic acid B) Homo Arecoline and C) Arecoline

Molecular Docking

Molecular docking analysis has opened a new perspective in understanding and advancing the knowledge on the DNA-ligand interactions. Further, it also provides useful

insights on the mechanistic aspect by which complex biochemical phenomena takes place. The molecular docking has been performed using Glide module in Schrödinger package to examine modelled interactive capability of the selected ligands with the cyclin binding region of CDK4. The ligands in their low-energy conformations were docked with the targets by considering both ligands and the DNA as flexible one using Induced Fit Docking (IFD) (22).

Molecular Dynamics Simulation

Molecular Dynamics (MD) simulation of the complexes were done using the desmond module (academic version) of Schrodinger software suite(23). The initial system for the MD simulation was set by using the system builder panel. The complexes were built in the orthorhombic box and solvated with SPC water models(24). The systems were equilibrated using the NPT ensemble, based on the default desmond options. The systems were then subjected to a 150ns simulation production run with a relaxation time of 2ps. During the simulation, 1 atm pressure and 300K temperature of the system were set using a Martyna-Klein barostat(25) and Nose-Hoover chain thermostat(26).

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The cyclin binding region of CDK4 (nucleotides 145-165) was modeled and prepared for use as the starting structure for molecular docking. Its known that the DNA is not rigid rather a very flexible molecule, and hence induced fit docking, which assumes the macromolecule to be flexible was performed.

Physicochemical properties of the molecules

Properties like hydrogen bonding, molecular flexibility, hydrophobicity, size, and the presence of pharmacophoric features influence a molecule's behaviour in biological systems. These factors impact its bioavailability, toxicity, reactivity, metabolic stability, interactions with transport proteins, and other aspects of its pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics. The calculated physicochemical properties are shown in Table 1. All the molecules share moderate molecular weight and Topological Polar Surface Area (TPSA). Nicotinic acid showed a moderate TPSA, suggesting its ability to cross the cell membranes.

Table 1: Physicochemical properties of the selected molecules

	MW	TPSA	natoms	nrotb	LogP
Nicotinic acid	123.11	50.19	9	1	0.78
Arecoline	155.19	29.54	11	2	0.36
Homo arecoline	169.22	29.54	12	3	0.75

Bioactivity Prediction

The bioactivity of the compounds was analysed based on the following criteria of drug activity.

1) activity on the G protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) ligand, 2) modulation of ion channels, 3) inhibition of kinases, 4) proteases, and other enzymes, and activity on nuclearreceptor ligands. Bioactivities of the molecules as predicted by Molinspiration is depicted in Table 2. A molecule with a bioactivity score greater than zero is considered to have good bioactivity. Scores ranging from -0.50 to 0.00 indicate moderate activity, while scores below -0.50 suggest inactivity (27). The results of bioactivity are showed in Table 2. Based on the scores, it is found that the molecules have the potential to modulate ion channels and can act as GPCR ligand.

Table 2: Bioactivity Prediction of molecules

Sl.No		Nicotinic acid	Homoarecoline	Arecoline
1	GPCR ligand	0.41	0.36	0.01
2	Ion channel modulator	0.10	0.04	0.31
3	Kinase inhibitor	-0.94	-1.00	-0.95
4	Nuclear receptor ligand	-0.81	-0.93	-0.74
5	Protease inhibitor	-0.87	-0.92	-0.73
6	Enzyme inhibitor	-0.31	-0.34	0.01

To further predict the higher efficiency and probable prediction of protein targets, Swisstarget prediction tool was employed. It was observed that the compounds have higher probability for family A G Protein Coupled receptor as evident from figure 1.

Figure_2: Predicted Biological targets of the selected molecules: Toxicity Prediction of the compounds

The risk of toxicity including mutagenicity, tumorigenicity, hepatotoxicity, cardiotoxicity and many more are predicted and reported in Table 3. All the three molecules were found to possess neurotoxic, respiratory toxicity, and toxic to blood-brain barrier.

Table 3: Predicted Toxicity of the molecules

Sl. No	Compound	Nicotinic acid		Arecoline		Homo Arecoline	
		Probability	Activity	Probability	Activity	Probability	Activity
1	Hepatotoxicity	0.80	Active	0.91	Inactive	0.93	Inactive
2	Neurotoxicity	0.57	Active	0.64	Active	0.65	Active
3	Nephrotoxicity	0.54	Active	0.62	Inactive	0.57	Inactive
4	Respiratory toxicity	0.73	Active	0.68	Active	0.71	Active
5	Cardiotoxicity	0.67	Inactive	0.69	Inactive	0.68	Inactive
6	Carcinogenicity	0.95	Inactive	0.69	Active	0.60	Active
7	Immunotoxicity	0.99	Inactive	0.99	Inactive	0.99	Inactive
8	Mutagenicity	0.99	Inactive	0.71	Active	0.53	Inactive
9	Cytotoxicity	0.77	Inactive	0.87	Inactive	0.86	Inactive
10	BBB-barrier	0.87	Active	0.93	Active	0.91	Active

Interaction of the ligands with the DNA

DNA-ligand binding occurs either by intercalation between base pairs or groove recognition (1). Non-covalent interactions can occur through intercalation between adjacent base pairs, groove binding, or electrostatic interactions with the sugar-phosphate backbone. Molecular docking studies were carried out to investigate the potential interactions of the selected ligands with the target DNA. All the compounds, namely Arecoline, Homo Arecoline, and Nicotinic acid, have the potential to bind with CDK4. To gain insight into the role of major and minor grooves in ligand binding, separate molecular docking experiments were performed for both major and minor grooves. The docking and IFD scores obtained are indicative of affinity between the chosen compounds and the DNA double helix. In general, although the major groove offers more H-bonding donor and acceptor sites, it has been suggested that it provides a much larger and shallow binding pocket for small molecule binding than minor groove. Indeed, most of the small molecule ligands bind to the minor groove, while the major groove is preferential for protein and peptide binding. However, we observed that both major and minor grooves exhibited good interactions with the ligands, with the minor groove demonstrating a stronger binding potential than the major groove as evident from the docking, IFD scores and Prime energies. The interaction of the chosen compounds with the major and Minor groove is tabulated in Table 4.

Table 4: Docking and IFD Scores of the interaction of ligands with the target DNA

Sl. No	Compound name	Major Groove			Minor groove		
		Docking score	IFD Score	Prime Energy	Docking score	IFD Score	Prime Energy
1	Arecoline	-5.087	-185.62	-3610.59	-5.937	-188.48	-3636.92
3	Homo arecoline	-5.579	-185.93	-3607.01	-6.529	-188.35	-3615.99
4	Nicotinic acid	-4.091	-182.80	-3574.12	-5.276	-185.43	-3587.84

Arecoline interacted with the DNA with a score of -5.087 Kcal/mol and -5.937 Kcal/mol for major and minor grooves respectively. In the case of arecoline-CDK4 binding, both the major

and minor groove contribute almost equally to their interaction, forming a single hydrogen bonds with both the grooves (Figure 1). Arecoline is a tetrahydropyridine compound with a methyl group at position 1 and a methoxycarbonyl group at position 3 of the 1,2,5,6-tetrahydropyridine moiety. The methoxycarbonyl group was found to have hydrogen bonded interaction with both the minor and major groove showing a bond distance of 1.64 Å and 2.15 Å respectively.

Figure_3: Binding modes of Arecoline with the major and minor groove of CDK4 represented in 2D (Right hand side) and 3D (Left hand side) representations.

The docking and IFD scores show correlation for all the complexes (Table 1), with the IFD score slightly lower in minor groove compared to the major groove. Similar to Arecoline, homoarecoline also exhibits a good interaction with the target through its methoxycarbonyl group, forming a hydrogen bond possessing a bond distance of 2.14 Å with the major groove of DNA. However, the minor groove lacks such a bonded interaction, instead providing a pi-cation interaction at the amino group (Figure_3).

Nicotinic acid interacted with the DNA molecule, resulting in a docking score of -4.091 Kcal/mol and -5.276 Kcal/mol for the major and minor grooves respectively. Unlike Arecoline and Homo arecoline, Nicotinic acid showed two hydrogen-bonded interactions with both strands (DC 7 of the leading strand and DG 7 of the lagging strand). in addition to a salt bridge involving the NH group (Figure_4).

Figure_4: Binding modes of Homo Arecoline with the major and minor groove of CDK4 represented in 3D (Right hand side) and 2D (Left hand side) representations.

Figure 3: Binding modes of Nicotinic acid with the major and minor groove of CDK4 represented in 3D (Right hand side) and 2D (Left hand side) representations.

As evident from the above results, it is noteworthy that the methoxycarbonyl group of the ligands play a crucial role in forming hydrogen bonds with the DNA molecule by acting as electron acceptors. It is observed that all the three molecules may form covalent interaction with the DNA especially with respect to the minor groove (as evident from N^+H). However, this can be confirmed by further quantum mechanical studies.

Molecular Dynamics Simulations

In order to enlighten the docking results presented above, we performed molecular dynamics simulations of DNA-Arecoline, DNA-Homo Arecoline and DNA-Nicotinic acid complexes. All the complexes were found to be stable throughout the 50 ns simulation time. A drift in RMSD was observed for Homo arecoline and Arecoline. However, they were found to be stabilized throughout the 50 ns run.

Figure_5: RMSD of the complexes

Figure_6: Rg and SASA plots of the complexes throughout the simulation run

Conclusion

This study underscores the critical role of the methoxycarbonyl group of the ligands in forming hydrogen bonds with DNA, acting as electron acceptors. All three molecules examined have shown potential for covalent interaction with DNA, particularly within the minor groove, as indicated by the presence of N+H interactions. To further substantiate these observations, molecular dynamics simulations of DNA-Arecoline, DNA-Homo Arecoline, and DNA-

Nicotinic acid complexes were conducted, revealing stability across the 50 ns simulation period. Notably, while RMSD drift was observed in Homo Arecoline and Arecoline, they eventually stabilized, reinforcing the complexes overall stability. This study also highlights the potential genotoxic risk associated with Betel Chewing, a cultural practice linked to the genotoxic potential of its metabolites. By integrating molecular docking and MD simulations, we have identified compounds capable of forming DNA adducts, suggesting possible DNA damage and associated toxicological effects. The interactions observed, particularly the hydrogen bonds involving the methoxycarbonyl group in both the major and minor grooves of DNA, further affirm the potential DNA-adduct forming properties of these compounds. Moreover, the bioactivity of these compounds, including their roles as ion channel modulators and GPCR ligands, alongside observed neurotoxicity, respiratory toxicity, and potential blood-brain barrier toxicity, emphasizes the need for further investigation. Future studies, particularly quantum mechanical analyses, are essential to confirm the covalent interactions identified and to deepen our understanding of the long-term biological implications of these interactions.

Conflict of interest- No Conflict of interest

References

1. Doll R. The geographical distribution of cancer. *Br J Cancer* [Internet]. 1969 [cited 2024 Aug 6];23:1–8. doi: 10.1038/bjc.1969.1. Cited: in : PMID: 5768436.
2. Anand P, Kunnumakkara AB, Sundaram C, Harikumar KB, Tharakan ST, Lai OS, Sung B, Aggarwal BB. Cancer is a preventable disease that requires major lifestyle changes. *Pharm Res* [Internet]. 2008 [cited 2024 Aug 6];25:2097–2116. doi: 10.1007/s11095-008-9661-9. Cited: in : PMID: 18626751.
3. Gupta PC. Betel quid and oral cancer: prospects for prevention. *IARC Sci Publ* [Internet]. 1991 [cited 2024 Aug 6];466–470. Cited: in : PMID: 1855897.
4. Anand R, Dhingra C, Prasad S, Menon I. Betel nut chewing and its deleterious effects on oral cavity. *J Cancer Res Ther* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2024 Aug 6];10:499–505. doi: 10.4103/0973-1482.137958. Cited: in : PMID: 25313728.
5. Su S-Y. Evaluation of Nationwide Oral Mucosal Screening Program for Oral Cancer Mortality among Men in Taiwan. *Int J Environ Res Public Health* [Internet]. 2022 [cited 2024 Aug 6];19:14329. doi: 10.3390/ijerph192114329. Cited: in : PMID: 36361205.

6. IARC. Betel-quid and Areca-nut chewing and some Areca-nut-derived nitrosamines [Internet]. IARC; 2004 [cited 2024 Aug 6]. Available from: <https://publications.iarc.fr/103>.
7. IARC. Acrolein, crotonaldehyde, and arecoline [Internet]. International Agency for Research on Cancer, World Health Organization; 2022 [cited 2024 Aug 6]. Available from: <https://publications.iarc.fr/602>.
8. Jayant K, Balakrishnan V, Sanghvi LD, Jussawalla DJ. Quantification of the role of smoking and chewing tobacco in oral, pharyngeal, and oesophageal cancers. *Br J Cancer* [Internet]. 1977 [cited 2024 Aug 6];35:232. doi: 10.1038/BJC.1977.31. Cited: in: : PMID: 836760.
9. IARC. IARC monographs on the evaluation of carcinogenic risks to humans : tobacco smoke and involuntary smoking [Internet]. IARC Press; 2004 [cited 2024 Aug 6]. Available from: <https://publications.iarc.fr/101>.
10. Shear M, Pindborg JJ. Verrucous hyperplasia of the oral mucosa. *Cancer*. 1980;46:1855–1862.
11. Hirayama T. An epidemiological study of oral and pharyngeal cancer in Central and South-East Asia. *Bull World Health Organ* [Internet]. 1966 [cited 2024 Aug 6];34:41–69. Cited: in: : PMID: 5295564.
12. Gupta PC, Pindborg JJ, Mehta FS. Comparison of carcinogenicity of betel quid with and without tobacco: an epidemiological review. *Ecol Dis* [Internet]. 1982 [cited 2024 Aug 6];1:213–219. Cited: in: : PMID: 6765307.
13. Iida Y, Okada S, Irifune Y, Goto S, Ishida K, Sato F, Yurikusa T, Asakura K, Tsuzuki A, Mukaigawa T. Clinicopathological Features of Buccal Squamous Cell Carcinoma with Focus on Patients Who Never Smoke and Never Drink. *Int Arch Otorhinolaryngol* [Internet]. 2023 [cited 2024 Aug 6];27:e551–e558. doi: 10.1055/s-0042-1755433. Cited: in: : PMID: 37876683.
14. Asmin PK, Nusrath F, Divakar DD. Occurrence and Distribution of Cancers with Emphasis Upon Oral Cancers in Registered Oncology Institutes of South India - A Retrospective Study. *Indian J Community Med* [Internet]. 2024 [cited 2024 Aug 6];49:120–130. doi: 10.4103/ijcm.ijcm_106_23. Cited: in: : PMID: 38425965.
15. Kamangar F, Chow W-H, Abnet CC, Dawsey SM. Environmental causes of esophageal cancer. *Gastroenterol Clin North Am* [Internet]. 2009 [cited 2024 Aug 6];38:27–57, vii. doi: 10.1016/j.gtc.2009.01.004. Cited: in: : PMID: 19327566.
16. Langie SAS, Koppen G, Desaulniers D, Al-Mulla F, Al-Temaimi R, Amedei A, Azqueta A, Bisson WH, Brown DG, Brunborg G, et al. Causes of genome instability: the effect of low dose chemical exposures in modern society. *Carcinogenesis* [Internet]. 2015 [cited 2024 Aug 6];36 Suppl 1:S61-88. doi: 10.1093/carcin/bgv031. Cited: in: : PMID: 26106144.
17. Ricci CG, Netz PA. Docking studies on DNA-ligand interactions: building and application of a protocol to identify the binding mode. *J Chem Inf Model* [Internet]. 2009 [cited 2024 Aug 6];49:1925–1935. doi: 10.1021/ci9001537. Cited: in: : PMID: 19655805.
18. Gilad Y, Senderowitz H. Docking studies on DNA intercalators. *J Chem Inf Model* [Internet]. 2014 [cited 2024 Aug 6];54:96–107. doi: 10.1021/ci400352t. Cited: in: : PMID: 24303988.
19. Shahabadi N, Farhadi R. Multispectroscopic and molecular docking studies on DNA binding of guaifenesin drug. *Nucleosides Nucleotides Nucleic Acids* [Internet]. 2021 [cited 2024 Aug 6];40:317–335. doi: 10.1080/15257770.2021.1872793. Cited: in: : PMID: 33463400.

20. Kim S, Thiessen PA, Bolton EE, Chen J, Fu G, Gindulyte A, Han L, He J, He S, Shoemaker BA, et al. PubChem Substance and Compound databases. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2024 Mar 8];44:D1202. doi: 10.1093/NAR/GKV951. Cited: in: : PMID: 26400175.
21. Banerjee P, Eckert AO, Schrey AK, Preissner R. ProTox-II: a webserver for the prediction of toxicity of chemicals. *Nucleic Acids Res* [Internet]. 2018 [cited 2024 Aug 6];46:W257–W263. doi: 10.1093/NAR/GKY318. Cited: in: : PMID: 29718510.
22. Hannon MJ. Supramolecular DNA recognition. *Chem Soc Rev* [Internet]. 2007 [cited 2024 Jan 26];36:280–295. doi: 10.1039/B606046N. Cited: in: : PMID: 17264930.
23. Desmond Molecular Dynamics System, D. E. Shaw Research,... - Google Scholar [Internet]. [cited 2024 Aug 26]. Available from: https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Desmond+Molecular+Dynamic+s+System%2C+D.+E.+Shaw+Research%2C+New+York%2C+NY%2C+2021.+Maestro+-+Desmond+Interoperability+Tools%2C+Schr%C3%B6dinger%2C+New+York%2C+NY%2C+2021.+&btnG=.
24. Mark P, Nilsson L. Structure and Dynamics of the TIP3P, SPC, and SPC/E Water Models at 298 K. *Journal of Physical Chemistry A* [Internet]. 2001 [cited 2024 Aug 26];105:9954–9960. doi: 10.1021/JP003020W.
25. Martyna GJ, Tuckerman ME, Tobias DJ, Klein ML. Explicit reversible integrators for extended systems dynamics. *Mol Phys* [Internet]. 1996 [cited 2024 Aug 26];87:1117–1157. doi: 10.1080/00268979600100761.
26. Hoover WG. Constant-pressure equations of motion. *Phys Rev A (Coll Park)* [Internet]. 1986 [cited 2024 Aug 26];34:2499. doi: 10.1103/PhysRevA.34.2499.
27. Husain A, Ahmad A, Khan SA, Asif M, Bhutani R, Al-Abbasi FA. Synthesis, molecular properties, toxicity and biological evaluation of some new substituted imidazolidine derivatives in search of potent anti-inflammatory agents. *Saudi Pharm J* [Internet]. 2016 [cited 2024 Aug 6];24:104–114. doi: 10.1016/J.JSPS.2015.02.008. Cited: in: : PMID: 26903774.